

Dataset university policies, procedures and statements

Wouter Vandenhole and Isabelle Zundel, Law and Development Research Group, University of Antwerp – version 1 (May 2026)

1. Introduction on methodology and structure

Searches were mainly conducted through snowball sampling. The initial searches were conducted in June and October 2025. Updates were undertaken in March and April 2026. Corrections and feedback can be sent to wouter.vandenhole@uantwerpen.be.

For human rights policies, the following search items were used: ‘Human Rights’ (and translations into Dutch, French, Spanish, Swedish, ...), ‘Human Rights Due Diligence’, ‘academic freedom’/‘liberté académique’, ‘parténariat responsable’.

For statements on Israel/Palestine, the following search items were used: ‘Gaza’, ‘Palestine’, ‘Israel’, ‘conflict’, ‘troubled world’, ‘Middle East’, ‘Israeli universities’.

Section two includes human rights policies and is geographically (and then alphabetically within regions) ordered. Initially, a distinction was envisaged between general and topic-specific human rights policies. General human rights policies include all human rights. Topic-specific policies focus on academic freedom, discrimination and harassment (diversity and inclusion) or sexual violence, for example. A distinction was also envisaged between human rights policies that apply internally, externally or both. For reasons of feasibility, at this stage, the dataset only contains general human rights policies that mostly apply externally, i.e. with regard to partners.

2. Human rights policies

Africa

SOUTH AFRICA

[North-West University \(SA\)](#)

Europe and Australia

AUSTRALIA

[Canberra](#)

BELGIUM

[Universiteit Antwerpen](#)
[Vrije Universiteit Brussel](#)

[VLIR](#)

[Université Libre de Bruxelles](#)
[ULiège: Charter of Ethics](#)
[Commission de guidance et de vigilance des relations internationales à risque](#)
[UCLouvain](#)
[Université de Namur](#)

[Universiteit Gent](#)
[Universiteit Hasselt](#)
[KULeuven](#)

FINLAND

[University of Helsinki \(RISK-I tool\)](#)

IRELAND

[University College Cork](#)
[Trinity College Dublin: investment](#)
[University of Limerick](#)

[National University of Ireland and its Member Institutions](#)

ITALY

[Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro](#)

[Università degli Studi di Padova](#)

[Università degli Studi di Pisa: Academic Panel on Research Security and Integrity \(PASIR\)](#)

NETHERLANDS

[University of Amsterdam](#)

[Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam](#)

[Delft University of Technology](#)

[Eindhoven University of Technology](#)

[University of Groningen](#)

[Universiteit Leiden: Committee on Human Rights/Conflict Zones](#)

[Maastricht University](#)

[Radboud University \(Nijmegen\)](#)

[Erasmus University Rotterdam](#)

[Tilburg University](#)

[University of Twente](#) (secondary source [u.today](#))

[Utrecht University](#)

[Wageningen University & Research](#)

GERMANY

[Freie Universität Berlin](#)

[Universitätsklinikum Ulm](#)

[Ruhr Universität Bochum](#)
[Technische Universität Darmstadt](#)
[Friedrich-Schiller Universität Jena](#)
[Universität Konstanz](#)

[Universitätsmedizin Mainz](#)

SWEDEN

[Lunds Universitet](#)

[Malmö Universitet](#)

UNITED KINGDOM

[University of Aberdeen](#) (under preparation Autumn 2025)

[University of Glasgow](#)

SLOVENIA

[Univerza V Ljubljani](#)

SWITZERLAND

[Université de Genève](#)

[Université de Lausanne](#)

3. Statements

Russia/Ukraine	Nature of measures	Scope	Date
University of Aberdeen (UK)	suspending its bilateral agreements with Russian organisations indefinitely *(does not prevent participation multi-partner international networks)		1 March 2022 22 April 2022
Durham University (UK)	Suspension bilateral research collaborations; no new	Institutions and other entities Russia & Belarus	16 August 2022
Universiteit Gent (BE)			
University of Glasgow	Suspend partnerships Hardship funds for students Explore support for Ukrainian students and academics	Russian and Belarussian academic institutions	9 March 2022
Humboldt-Universität (DEU)	Suspension Emergency aid fund	Russian partners in research and teaching	2 March 2022
University of St Andrews UK)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. suspending any programmes, collaborations or activities 2. If a collaboration or joint project involves Russian state funding, expectation staff to withdraw from it 3. Immediate divestment from 2 Russian holdings 4. Hardship fund 5. University of Sanctuary 	Moscow State University, MGIMO	11 March 2022
European Universities Association (EUA)			
Universities UK International (UUKi)	Twining		
Turkey	Nature of measures	Scope	Date
Universiteit Gent	most types of collaboration are excluded	Turkish universities	

OPT/Gaza	Nature of measures	Scope	Date
BELGIUM			
Universiteit Antwerpen	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. MoUs terminated 2. institutional collaboration agreements on hold 3. Multilateral projects (EU): continue; if EC finds involvement in HR violation, ask EU Commission to take action against partner (*Hebrew University of Jerusalem continued) 4. New bilateral projects: not unless shown project not linked to HR violations 5. New multilateral projects: assessment by EC (*new project with Tel Aviv University) 	Israeli institutions	<p>28 May 2024</p> <p>2 July 2024</p> <p>26 August 2025</p>
Vrije Universiteit Brussel	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No bilateral collaboration 2. consortia: 1 ended upon negative advice; 3 ongoing in October 2025 		
Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Suspension institutional collaboration 2. Suspend institutional research projects 3. Authorized bilateral talks to initiate collaboration 4. Not initiate institutional collaboration as part of European projects 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Israeli and Palestinian universities 2. Hebrew & Tel Aviv 3. Birzeit 4. Weizmann Institute 	<p>May 2024</p> <p>21 November 2024</p> <p>3 July 2025</p>
Universiteit Gent 1 Universiteit Gent 2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Discontinuation 2. Continue 3. Discontinue collaboration with <p>Implementation: No action in 2 projects: expiring by end of 2024 One 'consortium change' completed in Erasmus+: no longer direct collaboration of</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Israeli academic institutions 2. Israeli companies 3. Listed governmental and academic institutions: Agricultural Research Organisation - Volcani Centre – Kishon Drainage and River Authority – Israel Oceanographic 	<p>30 May 2024</p> <p>8 November 2024</p>

<p>Universiteit Gent 3</p> <p>Universiteit Gent 4</p>	<p>UGhent with Israeli university (no student exchange; no joint degree award)</p> <p>4. For new collaborations and those positively advised by the Human Rights Committee, where necessary, an additional declaration must be signed by the partner, stating that they distance themselves from and acknowledge serious violations of international (humanitarian) law</p> <p>5. Withdrawal from HorizonEurope project approved by European Commission</p>	<p>and Limnological Research – Migal Galilee Research Institute; Ben-Gurion University of the Negev – Holon Institute of Technology – University of Haifa – Tel Aviv University – Weizmann Institute of Science</p> <p>4. All partners</p> <p>5. OSTEONET (Tel Aviv University)</p>	<p>3 October 2025</p> <p>27 March 2026</p>
<p>UHasselt</p>	<p>1. No institutional collaboration with</p> <p>2. Consortia: no human rights violations</p> <p>3. Monitoring by Human Rights Commission</p> <p>6. Application for new collaboration turned down; ongoing one allowed to continue, but new research activities to be screened by Commission</p>	<p>Israeli universities</p>	
<p>KULeuven</p> <p>Secondary source</p>	<p>1. All existing European consortia collaboration continued</p> <p>2. New Horizon started</p>	<p>Technion</p>	<p>28 February 2025</p>
<p>ULiège</p>	<p>1. No institutional links bilaterally</p> <p>2. Multilateral collaboration (EU): action to be taken at EU level</p> <p>3. Screening of collaboration with companies/foundations:</p>	<p>1. Israeli universities</p> <p>2. Israeli partners</p> <p>3. Fondation Léon Fredericq; preventive measures OIP:</p>	<p>30 May 2024</p>

Uliège 2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Commitment to suspend all direct collaboration with partners who directly contribute/openly support military action in Gaza or do not respect human rights 5. Horizon: moratorium new projects/suspension ongoing ones pending screening 6. moratorium new projects/suspension ongoing ones pending screening 	suspension collaboration: PB Clermont et Mecar <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Israeli universities 6. Tel Aviv; Hebrew; Elbit System 	21 March 2025
CANADA			
Université de Québec à Montréal (CA)	Monitor interactions and investments	All universities	29 May 2024
FINLAND			
University of Hensinki 1 University of Helsinki 2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Exchange agreements suspended 2. no international sanctions have been imposed, selection of research partners continues to fall under academic freedom 3. no direct ownership in Israeli businesses or in companies listed by the international BDS movement 4. actively promoted the exclusion of Israel from projects funded under the EU's Horizon programme, both in Universities Finland (UNIFI) and in international network 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tel Aviv & Hebrew University of Jerusalem 	21 May 2024
FRANCE			
Sciences Po Strasbourg (FR) secondary source	termination	Reichman	31 October 2024
IRELAND			
Queen's University Belfast	Divest (from managed portfolio)	Israeli companies and companies on the UN blacklist	28 June 2024
University College Cork (IRE)	Mapping of existing partnerships; respect existing legal obligations; due diligence future		

	ones; strengthen collaboration Palestinian universities; academic freedom seminar series		
Trinity College Dublin (Recommendations Taskforce June 2025)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Fully divest 2. Suppliers 3. Commercial relationships 4. No further mobility agreements 5. No new institutional research agreements Align with like-minded to influence EU policy	All companies HQ in Israel No Israeli firms Israeli entities Israeli universities Israeli participation	5 June 2025
University of Limerick (IRE)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. no active partnerships with 2. no investments in 3. There are no Israeli companies providing funding for research or investments at UL. 4. partner of EU funded research project. UL respects the academic freedom of its staff to pursue international collaborations and research. 5. University of Sanctuary Scholarship/SAR/Gaza Scholarship Initiative 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Israeli academic institutions 2. arms manufacturing or distribution companies in Israel 3. Israeli companies 4. Israeli partner (not an academic institution). 	22 May 2024
National College of Arts and Design	Suspension (as of September 2026); no new	Israeli HEIs	30 September 2025
ITALY			
Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establishment of a system for monitoring projects underway with 2. activation of a ‘university corridor’ to allow Palestinian scholars as visiting researchers 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Israeli universities, institutions, and companies 	22 July 2025
Università degli Studi Firenze (five Faculties) secondary source	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Collaborations temporarily suspended 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ben-Gurion, Ariel, Blavatnik Centre Tel Aviv 	15 July 2025
Università degli Studi di Milano Statale secondary source 1 & 2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Suspend mobility agreement 2. Suspend mobility agreement 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ariel University 2. Reichman 	April 2024 October 2024

<p>Università di Padova</p> <p>Università di Padova 2</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. strengthening existing initiatives such as "Scholars at Risk" and "Students at Risk", by allocating resources for scholarships IUPALS 2. Promote shared position Italian universities Palestinian people's right to self-determination/recognition of State of Palestine 3. not undertaking new institutional agreements nor renewing existing ones with Israeli institutions and entities that contribute to the continuation of severe violations of international law and the illegal occupation of Palestinian territory 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Palestinian universities 2. 3. Israeli institutions and entities 	<p>14 May 2024</p> <p>1 July 2025</p>
<p>Scuola Normale Superiore</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. no cooperation agreements in place with Israeli research bodies and universities 2. Intensify participation in the initiatives of the "Network of Italian Universities for Peace", 3. not to enter into institutional cooperation or collaboration agreements with Israeli institutions, universities and research bodies which, upon closer examination, appear to be directly or indirectly involved in violence and occupation to the detriment of the civilian populations of Gaza and the West Bank 4. strengthen and consolidate the assessment and monitoring activities of the "Academic Panel on Research Security and Integrity" in order to ensure compliance with the above principles and 		<p>22 July 2025</p>

	continue internal training courses for the entire community.		
Università di Pisa	Suspend framework agreements	Reichman/Hebrew University	24 July 2025
NETHERLANDS			
KABK/Dutch Royal Academy of Art	Suspend exchange agreement; support fund	Bezalel University	10 May 2024
University of Amsterdam University of Amsterdam University of Amsterdam University of Amsterdam University of Amsterdam University of Amsterdam	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No extension of student exchange 2. Student exchange under consideration 3. Not enter new HorizonEurope collaborations pending EU investigation 4. Divest: no direct cash flows to or investments in Israel 5. Safe Haven Fellowship: UvA and Maastricht University are collaborating with NIAS in the Safe Haven Fellowship program (since February 2025) 6. 10 HorizonEurope involving Israeli partners; 6 began after outbreak conflict; 4 began after May 2024: ethical clearance and strict conditions: no direct data exchange; no direct collaboration in same work package 7. Reconfirmed: no new Horizon collaborations; no new institutional collaborations in education; not taking steps to extend student exchange with Tel Aviv (expiring next year); explore legal scope for withdrawing from current Horizon collaborations 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Hebrew University 2. Tel Aviv 3. Israeli organisations Gaza researchers Israeli partners Israeli partners	20 June 2025 11 September 2025 2 September 2025 15 October 2025
Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (Stichting VU)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. discontinue a specific research collaboration involving 2. Continues research collaboration with 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. an Israeli government body (Ministry of Health: PARC)? 2. Hebrew University of Jerusalem 	4 June 2025

Delft University of Technology update	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No new collaborations unless very demanding criteria of Moral Deliberation Chamber are met 2. Ongoing research projects continue but undergo critical assessment 3. 3 new collaborations declined since moratorium 4. 2 Horizon projects NeAlxt and E2PackMan signed after moratorium, but with declarations of honour signed in February and May; NeAlxt ended by mutual agreement 	<p>Israeli universities and organisations</p>	<p>10 June 2025</p> <p>3 December 2025</p>
Eindhoven University of Technology NOS	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Freeze institutional cooperation with 2. No new projects involving institutional collaboration until expert committee installed (envisaged: 15 July 2025) 3. Departmental collaboration continued: no direct contact; no risk gross HR violations 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Technion via membership of the EuroTech Universities Alliance 2. Israeli institutional partners 3. Technion 	<p>June 2025</p> <p>15 October 2025</p>
Gerrit Rietveld Academie	<p>Suspend collaboration; support fund</p>	<p>Bezalel Academy of Arts and Design & Jerusalem School of Visual Theatre</p>	<p>28 May 2024</p>
University of Groningen NOS Ukrant University of Groningen 16 October 2025 University of Groningen 31 October 2025	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No suspension student & staff exchange 2. Research collaborations continued <p>Also if high-ranking military officer is involved</p> <p>Temporarily suspended participation in React until review by Advisory Team</p> <p>Only partially suspended, pending review by Advisory Team</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. three Israeli universities 2. also involve Israeli organizations <p>Technion</p>	<p>10 May 2024</p> <p>15 October 2025</p> <p>16 October 2025</p> <p>20 October 2025</p> <p>31 October 2025</p>
Universiteit Leiden	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Suspend student exchange 2. No new student exchange 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Jerusalem & Tel Aviv 	<p>Mid-July 2025</p> <p>4 September 2025</p>

<p>Committee on Human Rights/Conflict Zones</p> <p>institutional research collaborations with Israeli partners: advise expected in March 2026</p>	<p>3. No new research partnerships pending work Committee</p>	<p>2. academic institutions in Israel that have comparable close relations with the Israeli military</p> <p>The research collaborations under review are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Resilience, ERC Synergy project with Ben Gurion University of the Negev 4. ISIDORe, EU project with the Weizmann Institute of Science 5. Graph Algebras, Marie Curie project with the University of Haifa 6. TAILOR, EU project with Bar Ilan University 7. AQUAPLAN, EU project with Bar Ilan University 8. EU GLOCTER, EU doctoral training programme with Reichman University 9. PARC, EU project with the Ministry of Health 10. SSb4DCheM, EU project with AHAVA Dead Sea Laboratories Ltd. 11. IMAGIO, EU project with Philips Medical Systems Israel 12. European Citizen Science, EU project with the Mofet Institute 13. RECOMB, EU project Medical Research Infrastructure and Development and Health Services Fund by the Sheba Medical Center (LUMC) 	
--	---	---	--

		<p>14. EJP RD, European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases with the Ministry of Health (LUMC)</p> <p>15. THRIVE (Tumor-Host interactions in liver cancer of childhood and adults), EU project (LUMC)</p>	
<p>Maastricht University 1 (NL)</p> <p>Maastricht University 2</p> <p>Maastricht University 3</p> <p>Maastricht University 4</p>	<p>1. Existing institutional collaboration frozen, refrained from entering new partnerships in 2024</p> <p>2. Country-level assessment finalized</p> <p>3. Scholarships for 5 Gazan students</p> <p>4. Suspend institutional strategic partnership</p>	<p>1. Israeli institutions/partners</p> <p>2. Israel</p> <p>3. Gazan students</p> <p>4. Hebrew University</p>	<p>11 June 2025</p> <p>3 September 2025</p> <p>31 October 2025</p>
<p>Radboud University (Nijmegen)</p> <p>Radboud Advisory Committee</p>	<p>1. Suspension of implementation of institution-wide partnerships (MoUs) + bilateral partnership Faculty of Philosophy, Theology and Religious Studies</p> <p>2. No new bilateral collaborations</p> <p>3. Not multilateral collaborations (consortia)</p> <p>4. Abandon proposed collaboration</p>	<p>Tel Aviv/Hebrew University</p> <p>4. Ben Gurion</p>	<p>21 May 2025</p> <p>4. November 2025</p>
<p>Erasmus University Rotterdam</p>	<p>1. Suspend collaboration</p> <p>2. Suspend collaboration</p> <p>3. Future institutional collaboration: distance themselves from involvement in HR violations</p> <p>4. International alliances/consortia: only participate if no direct collaboration with those universities</p>	<p>1. Bar Ilan</p> <p>2. Hebrew; Haifa</p> <p>3. Hebrew; Haifa</p> <p>4. Bar Ilan; Hebrew; Haifa</p>	<p>5 June 2025</p>
<p>Tilburg University</p> <p>Tilburg University 2</p>	<p>1. Suspend institutional collaboration</p> <p>2. NO decision yet</p> <p>Continue dialogue; no new institutional collaboration will be initiated; no active</p>	<p>1. Reichman/Bar Ilan</p> <p>2. Hebrew</p> <p>Hebrew</p>	<p>7 May 2025</p> <p>20 June 2025</p> <p>12 November 2025</p>

	implementation of existing student exchange agreement		
Utrecht University 1	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No reason to freeze or stop ongoing research collaborations 2. Student exchange: contract expired 3. Suspension due to negative travel advice (May 2025: terminated) 4. Not enter into any new institutional nor project-based collaborations until further notice 5. aims to withdraw from an ongoing project in which 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Israeli organizations 2. Hebrew and Reichman 3. Haifa 4. Israeli organizations 5. Israeli government (Ministry of Health) is one of partners 	18 October 2024
Utrecht University 2			16 May 2025
Wageningen University & Research	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Exchange agreement students 2. Euroleague for Life Sciences Universities 3. Research projects EU funding 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Hebrew University 2. Hebrew University 3. Hebrew University of Jerusalem; Ben-Gurion University of the Negev Reichman University; University of Haifa; Israel Oceanographic and Limnological Research Limited; Tel Aviv University; Weizmann Institute of Science; The Agricultural Research Organization of Israel 	2024?
NORWAY			
OsloMet	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Suspension 2. No new general cooperation agreements 3. Terminate purchasing agreements 4. Expand Scholars at Risk scheme 	Haifa Israeli Universities and Colleges Suppliers direct connection Israeli military or operate in OPTs	14 February 2024
University of South Eastern Norway (USN)	Discontinuation of exchange schemes	Haifa University and Hadassah Academic College in Jerusalem	19 February 2024
University of Bergen (UiB) Faculty of Art, Music and Design	Termination	Bezalel	December 2023

Bergen School of Architecture University of Bergen (UiB), Faculty of Law ¹	Termination Termination	Bezael Tel Aviv University	2023 19 March 2024
Nord University	1. Suspension of activities under exchange agreements (currently inactive) 2. Complying with EU regulations re participation in an EU-funded research project 3. Not enter into any new agreements 4. Joined NorPal	two different universities in Israel Israeli universities	23 February 2024
SPAIN			
Conferencia de Rectores y Rectoras de las Universidades Españolas - CRUE	1. Review and suspend collaboration; 2. Intensify cooperation with Palestinian HEIs	Israeli universities and research centres	9 May 2024
Asociación de Universidades Públicas de Andalucía	1. Review/suspend cooperation agreements with 2. Intensify cooperation with the Palestinian scientific and higher education system	1. Israeli universities and research centres that have not expressed a firm commitment to peace and compliance with IHL	9 May 2024
Universitat de Barcelona update state of affairs Faculty 18	1. No new collaboration agreements 2. Termination 3. Precautionary suspension internships 4. Call on EU: block participation 5. No participation in academic/institutional event	1. Israeli institutions 2. Tel Aviv 3. Companies allegedly linked to conflict 4. Israeli institutions 5. Israeli institutions	22 May 2024 18 June 2025
Universidade da Coruña	1. Publish collaboration; no support nor participation 2. Promote suspension Association Agreement: no participation in funding	1. Israeli companies, universities, institutions, public institutions	26 June 2024

¹ on 7 March 2024, the board of the University of Bergen declined to impose a general boycott against Israeli universities but gave authority to individual faculties to decide upon their own boycotts.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Collaboration with Palestinian universities 4. Establish Chair for Palestine 		
Universidad de Granada	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Suspension of mobility 2. Suspension of lectureship agreements & summer courses 3. No new agreements 4. Intensify collaboration with Palestinian 5. Suspension of scientific and technical cooperation 6. No new research collaboration 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. All Israeli universities 2. Bar Ilan & Tel Aviv 3. All Israeli universities 4. Palestinian uni and NGOs 5. All Israeli institutions 6. All Israeli institutions 	17 May 2024
Universidad de Malaga	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Suspend collaboration 2. Collaboration: hosting Palestinian scholars & students https://www.uma.es/la-uma-con-palestina/cms/menu/plan-propio-de-investigacion/ 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Tel Aviv, Technion International, Bezalel Academy of Arts and Design, Jerusalem & Ben-Gurión del Néguv 2. Palestinian universities 	30 May 2024
SLOVENIA			
Univerza V Ljubljani (SLO)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No active bilateral cooperation agreements 2. Participation in 4 EU funded projects <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Horizon Europe INFRA EMERGENCY: no direct collaboration between the University of Ljubljana and Israeli institutions • Horizon Europe SEAMAC: coordinator • 2 Erasmus+: no student exchanges with Israeli institutions 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Israeli universities 2. Also involve Israeli institutions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technion 	10 July 2025
SOUTH AFRICA			
University of Fort Hare (SA)	No institutional links	Israeli institutions	14 December 2023
Mandela (SA)	Boycott	Israeli academic institutions and academics/businesses if complicit	6 May 2024
UCT (SA)	No relations	Israeli Defense Force	22 June 2024
UWC (SA)	Disengage; investment transparency, commitment to divestment	Israeli academic institutions Israeli products and companies	28 June 2024

University of Venda (SA)	suspend	Israeli universities and institutions	3 June 2024
SWEDEN			
Lunds Universitet	No ongoing overall cooperation agreements in Israel or in the region	universities in Israel	
Stockholms Universitet	Stockholm University will not take a public stance in relation to	Israeli higher education institutions	21 May 2024
SWITZERLAND			
Université de Genève	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. guarantee transparency about collaboration with universities abroad: ends strategic partnership no renewal student mobility Feb 2026 2. strengthen ethical and deontological control 3. strengthen programs for students and researchers universities in Gaza 	Hebrew University Tel Aviv University	20 May 2024 3 June 2025 3 June 2025
Université de Lausanne	Terminate/suspend	Hebrew University of Jerusalem	2 May 2025
UNITED KINGDOM			
University of Aberdeen	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. no active Institution level agreements with universities in Israel and no intention to enter into any new agreements 2. Investment and procurement: review the potential to extend those exclusions to include the wider arms sector and the UN listing of companies involved in specific activities in Israeli settlements in the Occupied Palestinian Territories (*implementation timeline 10 January 2025: Pooled fund management means exclusion is not possible) 	universities in Israel	6 June 2024
OTHER			
European Association of Social Anthropologists (EASA)	1. not collaborate with Israeli academic institutions until Israel complies with	Israeli academic institutions	November 2024/July 2025

	<p>International Law and International Humanitarian Law and ends the occupation of the Occupied Palestinian Territory</p> <p>2. encourages its members not to enter into institutional arrangements, e.g. through common research projects and grants, and partnerships with Israeli academic institutions</p>		
--	--	--	--